

occurs in the Girnâr inscription, it is only "the beloved of the gods" in the Kâlsi one, the word "king" being omitted in it.

Instead of *idha*, i. e. "here," in the Girnâr inscription, the Kâlsi and the Kapure-di-garhî ones have *hida*. *Idha* seems to be a corruption of the Sanskrit *atra*, which is corrupted into *इथे* in the modern Maharâshtri dialect, and *hida* appears to be a corruption of the Sanskrit *iha*, which has become *hidâ* in the modern Kachhi dialect.

In the Kapure-di-garhî and Kâlsi versions the words "for the sake of soup" are omitted.

In the Kâlsi copy in place of the phrase *so pi mago*, i. e. "the deer however" of the Girnâr inscription, the phrase *se pi ye mige*, i. e. "the one which is the deer however" occurs.

In the Kapure-di-garhî inscription, the numbers of the animals slaughtered daily in the king's kitchen are given in figures also thus:—"Peacocks two, 2, deer 1."

It is to be particularly noted that the peacock, a very common bird in India, is excluded from the list of birds to which Aśoka has given a promise of safety in his *Ldt* edicts. This circumstance seems probably to have some connection with the surname *M a u r y a* of his family, on account of some particular ancestral rite of sacrificing peacocks, a rite which Aśoka could not have given up so easily. We see in the above edict that he could do without sacrificing a deer sometimes, but not a single day without killing peacocks.

INDIAN TRAVELS OF CHINESE BUDDHISTS.

BY REV. S. BEAL, B.A.

There is a Chinese book in two parts called *K'iu-fû-ko-sung-chüan*, which contains brief memoirs of Chinese Buddhist priests who visited India during the early period of the T'ang dynasty (618 A.D.—907 A.D.)—written by I-tsing of the same dynasty.

Altogether there are fifty-six names recorded in the index of the work, and I will proceed to give a brief summary of the history of each name, though not always in the order of the Chinese record.

I. Yüan Chau.

The Doctor Yüan Chau, a Shaman, was a native of Sien-chang of Tai-chau. His Indian name was *Prakâśamati*. He was of distinguished descent both on his father's side and that of his maternal grand-father. Arrived at manhood he determined to forsake the world, and become a priest. He purposed to visit the sacred places existing in India, and for the purpose of preparation proceeded to the capital to attend religious lectures there. And so in the middle of the *Chêng-kwan* period (638 A.D.) he proceeded to the Ta-hing-shing Temple, and there in the place where H ü a n C h i n g had taught he gave himself to the study of Sanskrit literature.

Then taking his religious staff he wended to the west, purposing to visit the spot where Buddha taught in the Jetavana Monastery.

Leaving *Kin-chau* (Lan-chow) he crossed the "drifting sands," and passing through the Iron Gates, he ascended the snowy peaks till he

reached the Fragrant Lake; and then pressing forward with fixed determination he passed through *Sha-li* and the *Tukhâra* country, and so through Tibet, where *Wen-shing-kung* ruled, he traversed North India, and gradually arrived at *Jalandhara*. But before reaching this place they were threatened by robbers in a narrow pass. But by the influence of some sacred words, the robbers were put to sleep, and so they escaped. Passing four years in the *Jalandhara* country, the *Mung* king (Mongol king) earnestly pressed the pilgrim into his service, and during that period studied with him Sanskrit literature. After this, passing southward he arrived at the *Mahâbodhi* district (Magadha), where he spent four years. Deeply regretting that he was not permitted to meet the immediate person (of Buddha), he nevertheless paid reverence to all the vestiges of his presence, and after studying various books he went on to the *Nalanda* monastery. Passing three years in this place he met two priests, one called *Shing-sien*, the other *Ratna* of Ceylon, (or it may be "a priest of Ceylon.") After this, ascending the Ganges, the king of the *Mung* (*Shan* for *Mung* in the text) detained him in his capital at the temple called *Sin-chê*, for three years. Finally, in consequence of the Chinese ambassador *Wang-yun* urging his return, he went back to *Lo-yang* by way of *Nepâl* and *Tibet*, having traversed more than 10,000 *lis*. Once again, in the middle of the *Lin-têh* period (665 A.D.), he set out to *Kâsmir* in company with a Brahman

Lo-ki-a-yi-h-to and others. Narrowly escaping death by robbers, he arrived in North India, and there again met the Chinese ambassador, who commissioned Yüan Chau and his companion Lo-ki-a-yi-h-to to go to Western India, to the country known as Lo-tû.¹ Passing through Balkh they came to the Nava Vihâra, where they paid reverence to the water pitcher of Buddha and other relics. Passing thence through the region of Sin-tu and the Dard people, they remained for four years with the Mung king, after which they went to the district of the Vajrâsana (Magadha) and also the Nalanda Temple. Thence returning through Nepâl and Kapisa, owing to the difficulties of the road during the period of hostilities with the Arabs, they went back and traversing India again Yüan Chau finally died in the country of Amaraât in Central India, aged 60 and odd years.

II. *Hwui Lun.*

Hwui Lun, a master (of the law), was a native of Sin-ko (Corea). His Indian name was Prajñâvarman. He quitted his own country inflamed with a desire to perform a pilgrimage to the sainted spots of his religion. Taking ship he arrived in Fuhkeên, and thence gradually journeying forward came to Loyang. There he was commissioned by the Emperor to follow the steps of Yüan-chau, who had gone to the Western Countries, and, having found him, to attend him as servant.

Having undertaken this, he went from place to place, paying homage to the sacred spots of his religion. He dwelt for ten years in the convent called Sin-ché, in the country of Amaraât (or Amaraât?). Thence going eastward he visited the convent called Tou-ho-lo-sse, belonging to North India. This temple was originally built by the Tou-ho-lo peoples (the Tokhari?) for the accommodation of their fellow countrymen. It is very rich and well supplied with all necessaries for food and convenience, so that no other can surpass it in this respect. The temple is called Gandhârasanda. Here Hwui Lun remained for the purpose of studying the Sanskrit language.

All priests who come from the North occupy this temple, as the Superior of it is a man of

great learning. They call the Temple Tashio (*i.e.* 'Great learning'). To the west of the temple is another belonging to the country of Kapisa. This temple is also very rich, and celebrated for the learning of its priests, who excel in the Little Vehicle. Buddhist monks of the North also dwell here. This temple is called Gunacharita. To the N. E. of the great Bôdhi (the temple just named) about a couple of stages, is another temple called Châlukya.

This is the one which was formerly built by a king of the Châlukya kingdom in South India. This temple though poor is remarkable for the religious life of its inmates. In more recent times a king called Jihkwan ('Sun-army,') built a new temple by the side of the old one, which is now getting finished, and in which many priests from the South take their residence. In short all the different districts (of India and its neighbourhood) have temples erected for the entertainment of priests belonging to the respective countries—all, except China, which has none: and so we pass and return under great difficulties.

Forty stages or so to the eastward of this we come to the Nalanda Temple. First taking the Ganges and descending it, we reach the Mṛigaśikhavana Temple. Not far from this is an old temple, the foundations of which alone remain—it is called the China Temple. The old story goes that this temple was built by Śrigupta Mahârâja for the use of priests from China. At this time there were some Chinese monks, twenty or so in number, who, having wandered away from Sz'chuen by the road known as Ko-yang (?) came out near the Mahâbodhi and there offered their worship. The king, moved with reverence on account of their piety, gave them a village of considerable extent, where they might remain and finally settle—twenty-four places in all. Afterwards the Tang priests having died out, the village and its land attached came into the possession of aliens, and now three persons belonging to the Mṛigavana Temple occupy it. This occurred about 500 years ago or so. The territory now belongs to the king of Eastern India, whose name is Dêvavarmanâ.

¹ The Lariké of Ptolemy, the Lâr of the Arab writers, and Lâtadêsa of the Hindus, corresponding to the Northern Konkan.—Ed.

He has given back the temple and its land to the villagers to avoid the expense of keeping it up, as he would have to do, if many priests of China came there.

The Vajrāsana Mahābodhi Temple is the same as the one built by a king of Ceylon, in which priests of that country formerly dwelt.

Going seven stages or so to the N. E. of this temple we come to the Nalanda Temple, which was built by an old king, Śri Śakyāditya, for the benefit of a Bhikshu of North India, called Rājabhaga. This temple has been completed by a succession of kings, and is now one of the most splendid in India.

CHINGHIZ KHAN AND HIS ANCESTORS.

BY HENRY H. HOWORTH, F.S.A.

(Continued from p. 20.)

VI.

We have seen how, on the death of Yessugei Khân, the Mongols, led by the Taijut under their chief Terkutai Kiriltuk, deserted his young son Temujin. Anbakhai the chief of the Taijut had formerly been the supreme ruler of Mongolia, and it was natural that his descendant should now succeed to the broken heritage; but, as we have seen, none of the Taijut chiefs were anxious for this honour, and it would seem that a very considerable power in consequence passed to Chamukha, the head of the Jajirat or Juriat tribe, who joined with the chief of the Kirais in helping Temujin to recover his wife. He seems to have become the most important chief on the river Onon, and, as we are expressly told in the *Yuan-ch'ao-pi-shi*, had control of the proper subjects of Temujin himself. The latter now went to live with him. They were apparently both young, and had long been close friends, so close that Chamukha is constantly referred to as Chamukha anda, *anda* meaning a life-and-death friendship among the Mongols. It is ratified solemnly by an exchange of presents, &c. In this case the friendship had begun when Temujin was eleven years old. The two had been playing together on the ice on the Onon, when Chamukha gave his friend a stone from the musk deer,¹ Temujin returned a ball of copper(?). Afterwards when the two boys amused themselves with archery, Chamukha gave his friend an arrow, having a point that would rattle, made out of cows' horn, while Temujin presented him with one made of cypress wood, and so they became *anda*. The pact was now renewed, and Temujin put a golden scarf he

had obtained among the Merkit about his friend, and also presented him with a mare which had been sterile for some years. Chamukha gave him in return a similar scarf he had taken from the Merkit Dair Ussun and also a white horse. They had a feast together at Khorkhon Akhjubur under the thick trees, and afterwards slept under the same blanket. The two friends lived thus together for about a year and a half. One day, as they were sitting together in front of a kikitka, Chamukha used an enigmatical expression which it is difficult to understand, and which was not understood by his companion. He said, "If we stop at the mountain the horses will get forage, if at the ravine the sheep and lambs will get it." Temujin, who was perplexed by the words, rode up to his mother to ask her to explain them, but before she could answer, his wife Burtê intervened, and said: In regard to this Chamukha, people have said that he loves the new and hates the old. He is tired of us. His words conceal some illwill against us. It is better we should not stay; we had better get away during the night.² The fact was that a natural jealousy had arisen between the two chiefs who were both ambitious. Temujin had doubtless designs of his own. He could not forget the position his father had filled, and to which he was the natural heir, and he had no doubt spent the previous few months in securing the adhesion of a large number of partizans. This we gather from what followed. Chamukha, on the other hand, was naturally of an envious disposition, and was, in fact, styled Sechen.³ Rashidu'd-dîn has preserved some Sagas about him. He tells us that Tokhtoa

¹ A so-called bezoar stone or perhaps merely a lump of musk.

² *Yuan-ch'ao-pi-shi*, pp. 57-59.

³ *i.e.*, the crafty or far-seeing. Erdmann, *Temudschin*, p. 225. Abulghâzi says it means in Mongol and Uzbek one

who is witty, and is equivalent to the Arabic *akil* and the Tajik (*i.e.* Persian) *bâ-khîred*. In his day, he says, it was applied to a good speaker (*op. cit.* ed. Desmaisons, pp. 79 and 80).

Mahmud, Kunwâr Pâl represents Kṛishṇa Râja, and the city of Pâtan is Kṛishṇagiri. The tale of the siege and storm and the pious Musalmans studying the *Korân* by lamplight is given, but Jâfar and Muzafar are read for Sayyid Pâsha and Sayyid Akbar. The Somanâth myth is more merciful to its heroes than that of Kṛishṇagiri as only one of them fell in the conflict, and the decapitation incident is absent, not unnaturally, as the idea of mutilation is abhorrent to a Musalman. Two heroes named Hamir and Vegad fighting on the side of Kunwâr Pâl may be the prototypes of Akbar and Avan Singh, while the faqir now at Kṛishṇagiri may be indebted for his existence to the descendants of the Kalifah Âbu-Bakr, who were nominated to the Kâziship of Pâtan by Sultân Mahmud. Whether the Kṛishṇagiri myth is a case of clear

pilfering, or whether history has repeated itself, is a question which must be left to experts to decide. It is not impossible that truth lies between the two. Friday is a favourite day for fighting with Musalmans, and the tradition of Somanâth may have been current at the time, and suggested to Akbar Pâsha a way out of his difficulties. Storms are not unusual in the Bârahmahal, nor is it anything extraordinary for Musalmans to read the *Korân* by night; that their tents should be left standing may be due to their being better tents and better pitched than those of their neighbours, and the leaders of a forlorn hope stand a fair chance of losing their lives even by decapitation. Some portentous vitality on the part of the trunks may not need the miraculous to account for it, but has no doubt been magnified by tradition.

BUDDHIST PILGRIMS FROM CHINA TO INDIA.

BY REV. S. BEAL, B.A.

(Continued from p. 111.)

The Nâlanda temple built by Śrî Śâkrâditya is four square like a city. There are four large gateways of three storeys each. Each storey is some 10 feet in height; the whole covered on the outside with tiles.

Outside the western gate of the Great Hall of the temple is a large stûpa and various Chaityas, each erected over different sacred vestiges, and adorned with every kind of precious substance.

The Superior is a very old man. The Karma-dana or Vihâraswâmi or Vihârapâla is the chief officer after the Superior, and to him the utmost deference is paid. This is the only temple in which by Imperial order a water-clock is kept to determine the right time. The night is divided into three watches, during the first and last of which there are religious services; in the middle watch, as the priests may desire, they can watch or repose. The method in which this clock determines the time is fully described in the *K'hi-kwei-ch'uen*.

The temple is called Śrî Nâlanda Vihâra, after the name of Nâgânanda.

The great temple opens to the west: going about 20 paces from the gate there is a stûpa about 100 feet high. This is where the Lord of the world (Lokanâtha) kept *Wass*

(the season of the rains) for three months. The Sanskrit name is Mûlagandhakoti. Northwards, 50 paces, is a great stûpa, even higher than the other; this was built by Bâlâditya,—very much revered—in it is a figure of Buddha turning the Wheel of the Law, S. W. is a little chaitya, about 10 feet high. This commemorates the place where the Brahman with the bird in his hand asked questions. The Chinese expression *Su-li-fau-to* means just the same as this.¹

To the west of the Mûlagandha Hall is the Toothbrush tree of Buddha. This is not the willow tree.

On a raised space is the ground where Buddha walked: it is about 2 cubits wide, 14 or 15 long, and 2 high. There are lotus flowers carved out of the stone, a foot high, 14 or 15 in number to denote his steps.

Going from the temple south to Râjagriha is 30 *li*. The Vulture Peak and the Bambu Garden are close to this city. Going south-west to the Mahâbôdhi is seven stages (*yojanas*): the same due south to the "Honoured Footprint." To *Vaisali* is 25 stages north. To the Deer Park 20 or so stages west. East to *Tamralipti* is 60 or 70 stages.² This is the place for embarking for China from Eastern

¹ But here I-tsing is in error.

² Note by Ch. Ed. :—A stage is equal to a *yojana*.

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CHINESE INSCRIPTION FOUND AT
 BUDDHA GAYA.

W. Griggs, Photo-lith. London.

India and close to the sea. There are about 3,500 priests in the temple at Nālanda, which is supported by revenues derived from land (villages) given by a succession of kings to the monastery.³

*Discovery of two Chinese Inscriptions
at Buddha Gayā.*

Here I make a digression from I-tsing's narrative to notice a recent discovery. Among the rubbish left round the temple at Buddha Gayā after the completion of the works undertaken there during 1878 and the following year at the expense of the Burmese Government, Mr. Beglar of the Archæological Survey found two stones bearing inscriptions in Chinese. From a letter attached to a rubbing of the larger inscription, I gather that the stone was found under 12 feet of rubbish.

The supposition that these inscriptions, or at least the longer one, might be in some way connected with Fa-hian, led me to think that it might be desirable to direct attention to the fact, that there are records in China of other pilgrims besides Fa-hian and Hiwen Thsang, who visited India during the early centuries of our æra, and that the notices we have of them, in the work of I-tsing, though not by any means so minute or exact as those of the two just named, are yet interesting and in some respects useful for the student. I purpose therefore, after briefly alluding to the inscriptions themselves, to continue the notices of the names and journeyings of the pilgrims referred to.

The first and shorter inscription⁴ gives us the name of Chi-I, a priest of the Great Han country, presumably the writer of it. It states that Chi-I having first vowed to exhort or encourage thirty thousand men to prepare themselves by their conduct for a birth in heaven, to distribute in charity 30,000 books relating to a heavenly birth, himself to recite as many books, then, in company with others,

³ With reference to Jih-kwan mentioned by Hwui Lun (*ante* p. 110), it may be noted that the name is the exact Chinese equivalent of Āditya-sena. And from the inscription of Jayadēva of Nepāl, A. D. 760 (vol. IX, p. 181), we learn that Ādityasena king of Magadha was the grandfather of Jayadēva's mother, and if we allow 80 years to three generations, this would place Ādityasena about A. D. 680—say 670—690, in perfect accordance with I-tsing's allusion to him.—Ed.

⁴ The head of the larger inscription stone is triangular and sculptured in three compartments. In the centre is Buddha in the *Bhumisparsa mūdā*—that in which he attained to Buddhahood. In each side compartment is a three-

travelled through India, and arrived at Magadha, where he gazed upon the Diamond throne and other sacred vestiges of his religion. After this, in company with some other priests he further vowed to continue his travels through India, apparently for the same purpose. Amongst the Priests referred to, there are three named, the first Kwei-Tsêih, the second Chi-I, the third Kwang-Fung.

Beyond this I am unable to find any sense in the inscription. The forms of the characters may possibly be as ancient as the Han dynasty. But as the inscription has nothing to do with the figures of the seven mortal Buddhas, and the Bodhisattwa Maitreya sculptured above it, I am inclined to think that the figures must have been executed after the inscription was placed *in situ*, and possibly much of the inscription itself erased.⁵

The second inscription dates from the *Tien-hi* year of the reign of Chên Tsung of the Sung dynasty, *i. e.* 1022 A. D., and is to the effect that a priest Ho-Yun went to Buddha Gayā with a view to worship the sacred relics of the place, and that whilst there, he carved a stone pagoda with a surmounting pinnacle and a square base 30 paces to the north of the Bodhi Tree in honour of the 1,000 Buddhas. He would have also inscribed an entire *Sūtra* if his funds had been sufficient, but in place of that he left behind him the record before us, which is a hymn in praise of (*Uddānam*,) the three bodies of Buddha and the three thrones they occupy.

The three bodies are first the *Nirmānakāya* (*fū-shin*), secondly the *Sāmbhōgakāya* (*po-shin*), and thirdly the *Dharmakāya* (*fū-shin*.) In relation to the first which represents the human body,—it is described as compassionate, ready and able to deliver men from the midst of the fire. The second is the body which has appeared in various forms through countless ages, ever aiming to prepare itself for the final

facéd figure, probably female, with six arms holding, perhaps, vajra, sword, bow, &c. Underneath each is a human head, with three indistinctly formed objects, apparently animal heads, on one side of it, and four on the other,—seven in each case. There can be no doubt the larger ones are figures of Vasudhārā, the same as those drawn (though badly) in Rājendralāla Mitra's *Buddha Gayā*, pl. xxxi. figs. 1 and 2 (see *Ind. Ant.* vol. IX, p. 115). The first slab is represented in the accompanying plate, which will also appear in the *Jour. R. Asiat. Soc.*—Ed.

⁵ Dr. Bushel thinks the inscription is complete, but owing to the broken state of the characters he fails to read it.—Ed.

manifestation as Buddha, when its aim would be accomplished. Praising the third body, or the *Dharmakāya*, he says: "Co-extensive with the universe and inhabiting all time—with excellences as innumerable as the sand or grains of dust—it is beyond all human character and transcending all human language."

The three seats or thrones are, first, that at Gayā, which is the centre (*navel*) of the earth, springing from the depth of the golden circle, on which all the Buddhas have overcome the armies of Māra, with their lion voice.

The second is co-extensive with the three worlds, reaching above the heavens—renewed ever after the destruction of the world.

The third is without beginning or end—unaffected by time or circumstance, imperishable as the body (of the Law) itself.

The inscription continues in the same laudatory terms, and ends with the statement that in the year above named, viz., A. D. 1022, two men called I-tsing and I-lin were sent from the Eastern Capital with a *kashāya* garment in a golden case which they hung above the Bodhi Tree—and which fact is recorded as supplementary to the hymn of praise of Ho-Yun.

These inscriptions are not of much value for any critical purposes, but are worth consideration because they shew the strength of the religious impulse that urged so many pilgrims from China to visit this sacred spot, and the sincerity of their belief in the virtue of their pilgrimage.

III. *I-tsing and other Pilgrims by the Southern Sea route.*

Now to continue in brief outline our account of the Chinese visitors to India:—

1. I-tsing (the author of the work from which we quote) left China towards the end of the year 671 A. D., and sailing from Canton proceeded to the islands of the Southern Sea, that is the district about Java and Malaka, and after two years' sojourn in different parts of this neighbourhood, he arrived at Tamralipti in 673 A. D. He remained here five months, and afterwards following his companion went on to Nālanda, and thence proceeded to Buddha Gayā to

adore the sacred vestiges of his religion. After this he returned to Fo-shai (Śrībhōja),⁶ where he was able to draw up and entrust to his friend the account of what he had seen, and the information he had gleaned, respecting Buddhism. He returned to China in 693 A. D.

2. I-tsing next⁷ refers to two priests of Corea, their names unknown, who, starting from Chang'an, and taking ship on the coast, proceeded to the Southern Sea. Having arrived at Shi-li-foshi (Śrībhōja) they proceeded westward to the country of Pulusse, and there died. We know with some certainty that the country of Pulusse is Sumatra.⁸ We may therefore place Fo-shai (Śrībhōja) to the eastward of Sumatra.

3. Hui Ning, a priest of Yih-chau⁹ (in Chi-li), left China by sea for the South in the year 665 A. D. and passed three years in the country called Holing. This is generally the equivalent of the Kalinga country, but it seems also to be used for the country along the coast of Pegu as well as to an island in the Southern Seas.¹⁰

4. Wan-K'i of Kiau-Chau (in Chi-li?) spent ten years in the Southern Seas, and was very learned in the language of Kunlun and partly acquainted with Sanskrit. He afterwards retired to a lay life, and resided at Shi-li-foshi (Śrībhōja). Kunlun, we know,¹¹ represents the islands of Condore.¹² The negroes of this island, or rather these islands, were generally sold as slaves, and their language and habits were much studied by Chinese travellers.

5. Mochadēva, a Cochin Chinese, (or, of Kiau-Chau) went to India by the Southern Sea route, and having visited all the countries of that part, arrived at the Mahābōdhi Temple, where he adored the sacred relics, and died æt. 24.

6. Kweichung, another priest of Cochin China, went by the Southern Seas to Ceylon, afterwards in company with a priest called Hün-chiu he proceeded to the Bodhi Tree and afterwards to Rājagṛiha, and being taken sick in the Bambu Garden (Veluvana), he died there aged 30 years.

⁶ Jul. *Méthode*, p. 103.

⁷ K. I. p. 7, 1.

⁸ Compare Bretschneider, "*The Knowledge possessed by the Ancient Chinese of the Arabs, &c.*" p. 16 n.

⁹ K. I. p. 11, 1.

¹⁰ Perhaps Pulo Lingam off the coast of Sumatra.

¹¹ Klaproth, *Nouv. Journal Asiat.*, tom. XII, p. 232.

¹² It is also so marked in the map illustrating Fah-hian's travels in the *Fo-koue-ki*. Bretschneider also refers to it, and confirms Klaproth's conclusion: he is mistaken, however, in saying that the name Kunlun, as applied to Pulo Condore, is first to be met with in the history of the Sung dynasty A. D. 960 (*op. cit.* p. 14 n.)

7. A priest of the Mahāyana school called Tang, or "the lamp" (*dīpa*), went with his parents when young, to the land of Dvārapati, and there became a priest. He afterwards retired with the Chinese envoy to the capital, and lived in the temple of Tseyan, where Hiwen Thsang had resided. Afterwards he went by the Southern Sea route to Ceylon, where he worshipped the tooth—and then proceeding through South India and crossing into Eastern India, arrived at Tamralipti. Being attacked by robbers at the mouth of the river, he barely escaped with his life; he resided at Tamralipti for 12 years; having perfected himself in the Sanskrit he then proceeded to Nālanda and Buddha Gayā, then to Vaisali and the Kusi country, and finally died at Kusinagara, in the Pari-Nirvāna Temple.

8. Two priests of Kao-chang (Turfan) going in company with a Chinese envoy through the Southern Seas, died on board ship. Their books (the *Yoga Śāstra* and others) *I-tsing* remarks are still at Shili-foshai.

9. Taoulin, a priest of King-chau (in Hupeh) and the district Kiang-ling, whose Sanskrit name was Śilaprabha, embarked in a foreign ship (Hajik—? Tajik), and passing through the copper-pillars¹³ stretched away to Lanka (Kama-lanka), and then keeping along the Kalinga coast (*i. e.* the coast of Pegu) they came to the country of the naked men. The king of this country behaved well to the pilgrim, and he remained there several years. He then proceeded to Tamralipti where he passed three years learning the Sanskrit language. After visiting the Vajrasana and worshipping the Bodhi Tree, he passed to Nālanda where he studied the *Kośha*, and after a year or two went to the Vulture Peak near Rājagṛīha, and finally proceeded to South India, and going through the Marāṭha Country¹⁴ in Western India he studied a work called the *Ta-ming-chau*, in Sanskrit the *Vedidhārapitaka*. The current tradition is that this work was in 100,000 ślokas, which, in a Chinese translation, would represent 300 chapters (*kiuen*), but that a great portion is lost—and that after the death of the great Holy One the spirit of the verses was preserved by Arya Nāgārjuna. Taoulin after this proceeded to Kāśmir and the country

of Udyāna, and dwelt in Kapisa, where he adored the skull bone of Buddha—he then returned by sea¹⁵ to Quēdāh (Kie-c'ha). He was here informed by some Northern Tartars (*hu*) that there were two priests in their country agreeing in description with some friends of his, he returned therefore to North India, where he died, aged 50 years or so.

10. Another priest called Tan-Kwong of the same district in China, went to India by the Southern Sea route, and having arrived at Ali-kilo (Arakan?) he was reported to have found much favour with the king of that country, and to have got a temple built, and books and images; finally he was said to have died there.

11. Hwui-ming, a priest from the same district, set out to go to India by the Southern Sea route, but the ship being baffled by contrary winds put in at Tung-chu (copper pillars) in Ma-yuen, and after stopping at Shang-king returned to China.

12. Hwui-ta, a priest of Kung-chow and the district of Kiang Ning, was a man of high family. He appears to have accompanied an envoy in a Persian ship to the Southern Seas. Having arrived at Fo-shai (Śrībhōja) he remained there six months studying the *Śabda-vidya*. The king was highly courteous, and on the occasion of his sending a present to the country of Mo-lo-yu (Malaya), Hwui-ta proceeded there and remained two months. He then went on to Quēdāh, and then at the end of winter went in the royal ship towards Eastern India. Going north from Quēdāh, after 10 days or so, they came to the country of the naked men. For two or three *lis* along the eastern shore there were nothing but cocoanut trees and forests of betel vines. The people, when they saw the ship, came alongside in little boats with the greatest clamour; there were upwards of 100 such boats filled with cocoanuts and plantains, they had also baskets, &c. made of rattan; they desired to exchange these things for whatever we had that they fancied, but they liked nothing so much as bits of iron. A piece of this metal two fingers length in size would buy as many as 5 or 10 cocoanuts. The men here are all naked, the women wear a girdle of leaves; the sailors in joke offered them clothes, but they made

¹³ Straits of Banca?

¹⁴ Lo-tù; it was by mistake suggested above (note, p.

110), that this might be the Lār of the Arabs and Lāta of the Hindus.—ED.

¹⁵ The Southern Sea route.

signs that they did not want any such articles. This country according to report is south-west of the district of Sze-ch'uan. The country produces no iron, and very little gold or silver; the people live on cocoanuts and some esculent roots, but have very little rice or cereals. Iron is very valuable, they call it *Lu-a*.¹⁶ The men are not quite black, of middling height, they use poisoned arrows, one of which is fatal. Going for half a month in a N. W. direction we come to Tamralipti, which is the southern district of East India. This place is some 60 stages or more from Nālanda and the Bodhi Tree. Meeting the priest called "Lamp of the Great Vehicle" (Mahāyāna-dīpa)¹⁷ in this place they remained together there one year, learning the Sanskrit and practising themselves in the *Sābdasāstra*. They then went on with some hundred or so merchantmen towards Central India. When about ten days' journey from the Mahābōdhi, when in a narrow pass, the road being bad and slippery, he was left behind and attacked by robbers, who stripped him and left him half dead in a ditch. At sundown some villagers rescued him and gave him a garment. Going on north he came to Nālanda, and after visiting all the sacred spots in the neighbourhood, he remained at Nālanda ten years, and then going back to Tamralipti he returned to Quēdāh, and with all his books and translations, amounting in all to 500,000 ślokas, enough to fill 1,000 volumes, he remained at Śrībhōja.

13. Shen-hung, a priest of Sin-chow, also went to Śrībhōja, where he died.

14. The priest Ling-wan having gone through Annam came to India and erected under the Bodhi tree a figure of Māitreya Bodhisattwa, one cubit in height and of exquisite character.

15. Seng-chi, a priest and companion of the former, went to India by the Southern Sea route. Having arrived at Samatata the king of that country, named Hars Harvardhana, an upāsaka, greatly revered the three objects of worship, and devoted himself to his religious duties; he had made day by day above 100,000 figures of Jemma, had read through the great *Prajña* consisting of 100,000 ślokas, and was most punctual in his acts of worship, &c.

16. A priest Chi-sze went to the south and resided at Shang-king near Cochin China; he then went south to Śrībhōja, and afterwards proceeded to India.

17. A priest Wou-hing, in company with the last, left Hainan with an easterly wind and after a month arrived at Śrībhōja. He then went in the Royal ship for 15 days to Malaya, in another 15 days to Quēdāh, then waiting till the end of winter, going west for 30 days they arrived at Nāgavadana (Nāgapatam?), whence after two days' sea voyage they came to Sinhapura (Ceylon). He there worshipped the sacred tooth, and then, going N. E. for a month, arrived at the country of O-li-ki-lo? (Arakan). This is the eastern limit of East India. It is a part of the country of Champa (Siam). Staying here one year, he moved towards Eastern India with his companion Chi-sze. This place is about 100 stages from Nālanda. After this he proceeded to the Mahābōdhi Temple in the Mung country (*i. e.* the temple of Khardāh). Having rested here, he again returned to Nālanda, and studied the *Yoga, Kosha*, and other works. Moved with a desire to find copies of the *Vinaya*, he again repaired to the Khardāh (*Kie-lo-c'ha*) temple. About two stages from this he speaks of a saintly artizan, who by practising the rules of the Bodhisattwa Channa, expected to obtain the power of entering the dim caverns of earth. In the end he died at Nālanda.

18. Fā-chin also started by the southern route, and after passing Shang-king (Saigon) Ku-long, Kaling, and Quēdāh, he died.

19. Ta-tsing (I-tsing?) of Laichow (of Hunan) returned to the Southern Seas in 682 A.D., and after sending his books and images to China, resided at Śrībhōja, where he acted as interpreter of the Kiu-lun language. He returned to Chang'an in 693 A. D.

There is a note in I-tsing's other work (*Nan-hae-k'hi-kwai-niu-fū-chu'en*, K. I. p. 3) which throws some light on the geographical terms used in his former book. The note is to this effect. "Going east from Nālanda 500 stages, *i. e.* 500 *yojanas*, all this country is called the Eastern frontier. At the extremity of this frontier country are the great black mountains, the southern boundary of Tu-fan. The

¹⁶ *Loha* in most of the Sanskrit languages.

¹⁷ This must be the priest Tang referred to above.

record says that this is S. W. of Sze-chu'an. Going S. W. one month's journey or so, we come to Sz'ling; south of this is the border of the sea and the country called Śrikshetra; S. E. of this is Langkâva (Kamalañka); E. of this is Dvârapati; eastward of this at the extreme frontier is the country of Lin-i (Champa),—this country excessively honours the three objects of worship, and has many religious people."

With respect to the countries of the Southern Seas, I-tsing has, on the same page, the following note:—"Counting from the west there is first of all the P-o-l-u-s-se country (Sumatra), next the Malaya country, which is the same as that now called Sh-i-l-i-f-o-y-a-o-u country, next (or this is) the Mahâsin country (Sinhapura?), next is the Kalinga (Linga?) country, then the Tan-tan country (Natuna according to Bretschneider, *Arabs*, &c. p. 19, vide also *H. Thsang*, tom. I, p. 451), after this is the Pan-pa-n country (Banka?), after this is P-o-li (Biliton), after this Kiu-lun(?), then Fo-shai-pa-lo (Śrībhōja and Bali?), then A-shen and Mokia-man; and other islands not worth mentioning." All these countries, I-tsing remarks, "reverence the law of Buddha—they follow principally the Little Vehicle, but in Malaya the Great Vehicle is also slightly observed. These islands are some of them 100 *li* round, others several hundred, and others perhaps a hundred stages (*yojanas*)."

The southern point of Champa (Cochin China) is Shang-king (Saigon?), this is the same as Lin-i, the people of this country belong to the Sammatīya School, and also to the Sarvâstivâdins. S. W. of this one month (by land?) is Fu-nan (Camboja). The people of this country were formerly naked savages, and sacrificed to the gods, but afterwards were converted to Buddhism. But a wicked king has now driven the priests away and destroyed them, so that none but heretics are found here. This is the extreme southern corner of Jambudwīpa.

We observe that I-tsing frequently speaks of the *ten* countries or islands of the Southern Seas.¹⁸ These are probably the ten islands spoken of above. And so (on p. 8, K. II.)

he says there are twenty and odd countries between the Mahâbôdhi and Lin-i (*i.e.* Cochin China), whilst in the Southern Sea there are *ten* countries besides Ceylon; on the west, beyond the Great Sea, are the countries of P-o-l-i-s-se (Persia) and T-a-s-h-i (Arabia).¹⁹ The situation of Sh-i-l-i-f-o-s-h-a-i (Śrībhōja) appears to be settled by a notice (in the 3rd book and 24th p.,) where I-tsing says that in this place in the middle of the 8th month there is no shadow, and in the middle of spring the same. If the Chinese months are here referred to, this statement would place Śrībhōja as nearly as possible on the Equator—perhaps on the east coast of Sumatra, opposite Banka. But as the months in China are uncertain, we may still be at liberty either to place Śrībhōja on the Malayan Peninsula—or as far south as Surabaya in Java.

Putting together the notices to be found in I-tsing's works, we may conclude that the sea route between China and India in the early years of the Tang dynasty was by way of Java, Sumatra, the Straits of Malaka, the coast of Burma and Arakan, to Tamralipti, or else by the more adventurous way of Ceylon from Quēdâh. It seems that the Condore Islands were a centre of trade, and that the language of the natives of these islands was used generally through the Southern Seas—at least I-tsing speaks of himself as interpreting this language at Śrībhōja.

We have one or two points of some certainty in the itinerary of these pilgrims. For instance in the *Si-yu-ki* (tom. II, p. 82) we read that to the N. E. of Samatâta is the country called Śrikshetra, to the S. E. of this is Kamalañka; to the east of this is Dâapati (read Dvârapati). This country has been identified by Capt. St. John (*Phœnix*, May 1872) with old Tung-u and Sandoway in Burma, lat. 18° 20' N. long. 94° 20' E.; it is in fact the "door land" between Burma and Siam; this latter being called Champa or Lin-i. Hiwan Thsang remarks that to the S. W. of Lin-i or Siam is the country of the Yavanas, or as they are called in his text the Yen-mo-na. We do not read of this country in I-tsing; it may probably represent Camboja.

(To be continued.)

¹⁸ N. H. K. I. 25, &c. and also K. I. 2².

¹⁹ In Bretschneider (*Arabs*, &c. p. 8) we read that the king of the Ta-shi by name *Hin-mi-mo-mo-ni* in the year

651 sent for the first time an envoy with presents to the Chinese court, and at the same time announced in a letter that the house Ta-shi had reigned 34 years and had three kings.

or fifteen years. Fifteen years ago a Mâli or gardener set up the idol,¹⁰ and began to cheat the people by stating that it had appeared there of its own accord. Both men and women visit the temple and worship the idol. The very strange fact regarding this worship is, says the writer, that the worshippers, before commencing the worship, strip naked, apply powdered sandalwood to their whole bodies, put on the ornaments they may have, hold a small branch of the nimb tree in their folded

hands, and leave their places of residence to visit the idol. After visiting the idol, they go round the temple for a certain number of times. They then leave the temple to bathe in a neighbouring tank. After bathing, they return to the temple, worship the idol and return home. The writer wishes that this indecency should be put down. He states that when the Hon. Mr. Chapman, the present Chief Secretary to Government, was Collector of Sâtârâ, he punished some of the naked worshippers."

BUDDHIST PILGRIMS FROM CHINA TO INDIA.

BY THE REV. S. BEAL, B.A.

(Concluded from p. 197.)

IV. *Other Pilgrims who reached India mostly by the Northern route.*

1. Tao Hi, a Doctor of the Law, a man of the district Lih-shing, of the department Ts'ai chau (Shan-tung ?), his Sanskrit name Śridêva. He was a man of noble descent. Having gone through India visiting the sacred places, he came to the Mahâbodhi, where he remained several years, and then proceeded to Nâlanda. He likewise visited the country of Kusi(nagara). The Mung king of the Amaravat country greatly respected him. Whilst remaining at Nâlanda he studiously applied himself to the Great Vehicle. He resided also in the Chu-po-pun-na (the garden of the cremation; the Temple of the Nirvâna), and studied the *Vinayapitaka*, and the *Śabdavidya*. Whilst in the Ta-hsio temple (the Mahâbodhi) he engraved a memorial tablet in the Chinese language. He left more than 400 volumes, new and old, in Chinese, *Sûtras* and *Śâstras*, at Nâlanda. I-tsing did not meet him (he fell sick in the Amaravat country, and died aged 50 years or so), but he saw his chamber.

2. Sse-pin, a Doctor of the Law, a man of Ts'ai-chau, went after Huan-chin through North India, and then through Western India, till he came to Amârakûva. He there dwelt in the royal temple in high favour with the king. Here he met Tao-hi, a fellow townsman. After remaining here one summer, he sickened and died *œt.* 35 years.

3. Âryavarma, a Corean, in the middle period *Chêng-kwan*, 638 A.D., left Chang'an and came to Nâlanda, where he engaged himself in

copying many *Sûtras*, and was deeply versed in the *Vinaya* and *Abidharma*. After going eastward and visiting the Cock-foot mountain, and bathing in the Dragon-pool to the westward, he died at Nâlanda *œt.* about 70.

4. Hwui-Nieh, a Doctor of the Law, a Corean, in the middle of the *Chêng-kwan* period, 638 A.D., went to the west and dwelt in the Bodhi temple, where he adored the sacred relics and then went to Nâlanda, where he dwelt for a long time, reading and studying. I-tsing when arranging some Chinese books suddenly saw under the title this record, "Whilst dwelling under the Tooth-brush tree, the Corean priest Hwui-Nieh wrote this record." On enquiry at the temple, the priests said that he died there the same year, about 60 years of age. The Sanskrit books he wrote were preserved at Nâlanda.

5. Yuan Ta'i, a Doctor of the Law, a Corean, called by the Sanskrit name of Sarvajñânadeva. In the year *Yung-hwei* (650 A.D.) he went by the Thibetan road through Nepâl to Middle India; he there worshipped the relics at the Bodhi Tree, afterwards going to the Turkhâra country he met Tao-Hi, with whom he returned to the Ta-hsio temple (Mahâbodhi). Afterwards he returned to China, and was not heard of again.

6. Yuan-hau, a Doctor of the Law, a Corean, went with YUAN-CHIN in the middle of the *Chêng-kwan* period to India, and reaching the Ta-hsio temple, he died there.

7. Bodhidharma, a man of the Turkhâra country, of great bodily size and strength,

¹⁰ The principal shrine or temple of Ellammâ is at Ugar-gol near Saundatti in the Belgaum district, and is certainly a very old one, and so probably is the idol. It would be

interesting to know the details of its history within recent times.—ED. I. A.

came to China, and became a priest. He wandered through the nine provinces begging as a religious mendicant. Afterwards going to India to adore the sacred vestiges, I-tsing met him at Nālanda. Afterwards he went to North India and died when 50 years old or so.

8. Taou-lih, a Doctor of the Law, of Ping-chau, went by way of the sandy desert and the Tsih rock to Nepāl, and afterwards came to the Ta-hsio temple, where he remained several years; he then returned to Nepāl where he still is.

9. Taou-sing, a Doctor of the Law, of Ping-chau, called in Sanskrit Chandradēva, in the last year of the *Chéng-kwan* period (649 A. D.) went by the Tu-fan road to mid India; he arrived at the Bodhi temple where he worshipped the Chaityas; afterwards going to Nālanda, he was there much honoured by the king on account of his youth. After that, going twelve stages to the eastward, he came to the King's temple, where they study only the Little Vehicle. He remained here many years, learning the books of the *Tripitaka* according to the Hinayāna. Returning to China through Nepāl, he died.

10. Shang-tih, a contemplative priest, of Ping-chau. He longed with devotion for the joys of the Western Paradise, and with the view of being born there he devoted himself to a life of purity and religion (reciting the name of Buddha). He vowed to write out the whole of the *Prajña Sūtra*, occupying 10,000 chapters. Desiring to worship the sacred vestiges, and so by this to secure for himself the greater merit with a view to a birth in that heaven, he travelled through the nine provinces, desiring, wherever he went, to labour in the conversion of men and to write the sacred books. Coming to the coast he embarked in a ship for Kalinga. Thence he proceeded by sea to the Malaya country, and thence, wishing to go to mid India, he embarked in a merchant ship for that purpose. Being taken in a storm, the ship began to founder, and the sailors and merchants were all struggling with one another to get aboard a little boat that was near. The captain of the ship being a believer, and anxious to save the priest, called out to him with a loud voice to come aboard the boat; but Shang-tih replied, "I will not come; save the other people," and so he remained silently absorbed, as if his

short term of life were agreeable to one possessed of the heart of Bodhi. Having refused all help, he clasped his hands in adoration, and looking towards the West he repeated the sacred name of Amita, and when the ship went down these were his last words. He was about 50 years of age. He had a follower, unknown to me, who also perished with his master, also calling on the name of Amita Buddha.

11. Matisinha, a man of the capital; his common name being Wong-po. This man accompanied the priest Sse-pin, and arriving at the middle land dwelt in the Sin-ché temple. Finding his progress little in the Sanskrit language, he went to Nepāl, and died on the way there, *æt.* 40.¹

12. Yua-n-hwui, a Doctor of the Law, son of a general, according to report. Leaving North India he dwelt in Kaśmir and took charge of the royal elephants. The king of this country delighted day by day in going to the different temples, the Dragon-lake Mountain temple, the Kung-Yang temple. This is where the 500 Rahats received charity. Here also the venerable Madhyantika, the disciple of Ānanda, converted the Dragon king. This priest exhorted the king of Kaśmir by a great exercise of royal clemency to remit the punishment of more than 1,000 persons who were condemned to death. The king in consequence let them go. Having remained here some years he went southwards, and came to the great Bodhi temple, where he worshipped the Bodhi tree, beheld the Lake of "Muchin" (Muchhalinda),² ascended the Vulture Peak, &c. After this he went back to Nepāl and died there.

13. Again there was a man who accompanied the envoy by the northern route to the Turkhāra country, and there lodged in the Nāva-vihāra. In this establishment the principles of the Little Vehicle were taught. Having become a priest he took the name of Chittavarma. Having received the precepts he declined to eat the three pure things, on which the Master of the Convent said, "Tathāgata, our Great Master, permitted these five things³ as food, why do you object to them?" He answered: "All the Books of the Great Vehicle forbid them, this is what I formerly practised. I cannot now bring myself to change." The Superior answered,

¹ Nepāl has a poisonous medicine which kills many.

² Conf. St. Julien, *Mém. sur les Cont. Occ.*, tome I,

pp. 348, 378.

³ Vil. Jul. II. 2, n. 2.

"I have established a practice here in agreement with the three sacred collections, and you follow your own interpretation, which is contrary to mine. I cannot permit this difference of opinion, I cease to be your Master." Chittavarma was thus reluctantly obliged to yield. Then having learned a little Sanskrit he returned by the northern route. I know no more about him.

14. Again there were two men who lived in Nepál, they were the children of the wet-nurse of the Duke-prince of Tibet (Tu-fan). They both were ordained, but one went back to lay life. They lived in the temple of the Heavenly Kings. They spoke Sanskrit well, and understood Sanskrit books.

15. Lung, a Doctor of the Law; I know not whence he came. In the *Chêng-kwan* period, 627—650 A.D., he went by the northern route to North India, wishing to visit the sacred spots. In mid India he got a Sanskrit copy of the *Fá-hwa* (Lotus of the Good Law), and having gone to Gandhára he died there.

16. Ming Yuen, a man of Yih-chau, a Doctor of the Law, whose Sanskrit name was Chintâdêva. He embarked in a ship of Cochin China and came to the Kalinga country and thence to Ceylon. Whilst the king was engaged in worship, this priest, concealing himself in a private chamber, tried to steal the Tooth-relic with a view to bring it to his own country and worship it. He had it concealed in his hand and was taking it away,* when by careless exposure of it he was detected, and driven disgracefully away. He went to South India, and it was related that he was going towards the Mahâbodhi, but then losing all power of digestion he died on the road, where he had rested. I know not what his age was.

They now keep this Tooth-relic carefully guarded in a high tower. It is locked up and sealed by five officers, and when opened, great uproar (of music?) is made, through the town and outskirts. It is worshipped every day with flowers and incense; when taken out it is placed on a golden flower, and its brilliancy is everywhere diffused. A tradition says that if this relic were lost then the Rakshas would devour (it?). There is also a tradition which says that some day it will be taken to China, but this must be by Divine interference and not by human contrivance.

17. I-long, a priest of Yih-chau, well versed

in the *Vinayapitaka* and in the interpretation of the *Yoga*, set forth from Chang'an with a priest Chi-ngan of his own province, and an eminent man called I-huan; after travelling through the Southern Provinces, they came to Niau-Lui, and there embarked on board a merchant ship. Having arrived at Lang-kia (Kamalañka?) Chi-ngan died. I-long with his other companion went on to Ceylon, where they worshipped the tooth, and having obtained various books returned through Western India. It is not known where he is now residing. He has not been heard of in mid India.

18. H w u i Y e n, a Doctor of the Law, and a disciple of Hing-Kung, went with his master to Singala (Siñhala), and died there.

19. Sin-chin, a Doctor of the Law, his country not known. His Sanskrit name Ch ar i t a v a r m a. Taking the northern route he arrived in the Western country, and lived in the Sin-ché temple. In an upper room of this temple, he constructed a sick chamber, and left it for ever for the use of sick brothers. He himself died here. Some days after the beginning of his illness in the middle of the night he suddenly exclaimed:—"There is Bodhisatwa with outstretched hand beckoning me to his lovely abode"—and then closing his hands with a long sigh he expired, *æt.* 35.

20. Sanghavarma, a man of Samarkand, when young crossed the sandy desert and came to China. Afterwards, in company with the envoy he came to the Great Bodhi temple and the Vajrasana, where he burnt lamps in worship for seven days and seven nights. Moreover, in the Bodhi Hall, under the Tree of Aśoka he carved a figure of Buddha and Kwan-tseu-tsai Bodhisatwa (*i.e.* Avalôkitesvara). He then returned to China. Afterwards being sent to Kwai-chau (Cochin China), there was great scarcity of food there. He daily distributed provisions, and was so touched by the sorrows of the fatherless and bereaved orphans, that he was moved to tears as he visited them. He was on this account named the weeping Bodhisatwa. He died shortly afterwards from infection caught there, which soon terminated fatally, *æt.* about 60.

21. Wan-yun, a Doctor of the Law, of Lo-yang, travelling through the southern parts of China came to Cochin China, thence went by ship to Kalinga, where he died.

* This story has its parallels in the thefts of relics by pilgrims in the middle ages.—Ed.